

The 3-Day SDG Challenge: Active Learning Strategies for IS Education.

NWISEd Workshop on:
Co-Creating New Ways of Information
Systems Education.

Abstract

Sustainability refers to the achievement of present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. While prior research has highlighted the potential of Information Systems (IS) to support sustainability objectives - for instance, through supporting eco-efficient work practices and democratising healthcare access - our understanding of how to integrate the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a core aspect of IS teaching and curricula remains nascent. Promoting sustainability challenges can help students to adopt a more systematic perspective of IS and go beyond lifecycle considerations to question the potential impacts and consequences of IS solutions (van der Have & Rubalcaba, 2016; Suseno and Abbott, 2021; Butler, 2011; Markus and Mentzer, 2014). Similarly, further research is required to understand sustainability-driven design approaches promoting students' ability to solve problems using digital technology (Matthe and Turpin, 2019). There is a need to cognitively shift thinking and to adopt sustainability as an opportunity rather than a risk (Harris, et al., 2011). This requires the design of new problem-solving approaches which foster new graduate attributes, such as social responsibility, global citizenship, and digital competency. This teaching case study presents a pedagogical design and teaching method for embedding sustainability in systems design education using design thinking and 'active learning' techniques. The case study focuses on a 3-day student design workshop involving 17 hours of dialogue where students sought to create concept-driven designs of digital offerings which addressed a sample of selected problem statements in relation to SDGs 3 – Health and Wellbeing, 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, and 11 – Sustainable cities and communities. Going through a series of group-based challenge activities, students began with ideations, crash testing ideas, to the development of concepts, incorporating visualisations and business models. These activities were supported by feedback rounds with external experts in IS, design thinking, and the business marketplace.

Throughout this 3-day workshop, we were able to use active learning to support students' engagement with the problem statement ideation, concept formation, and business planning stages utilising techniques such as storyboards, user journeys, personas, ideation games, and business resilience tests through scenario challenges hosted on a Miro Board. These active learning methods provided students with a 'safe space' for tackling key sustainability challenges.

The four problem statements selected by the student groups included:

- I. How can digital solutions reduce the proportion of victims of physical/ sexual harassment (e.g., by sex, age, disability status, and place of occurrence)?*
- II. In what way can we prevent the incidence of non-communicable diseases through digital*

solutions and promote healthy lifestyles for lower socio-economic groups?

III. *How can digital solutions help provide resources and/or financial support to small companies?*

IV. *How can we use digital technology to prevent the spread of communicable diseases?*

In response to these SDG challenges, each group proposed two potential lines of inquiry for ideation and concept formation. Each stage of development was interspersed with peer review and group reflection, allowing time to consider feasible alternative routes of action.

Out of this 3-day workshop students proposed a range of digital solutions in response to the problem statements (see Table 1).

<i>Problem Statement No.</i>	<i>Proposed Solution</i>
<i>I</i>	<i>An AI system to raise awareness of physical/sexual assault.</i>
<i>II</i>	<i>Improve the sustainability of food products through data analytics.</i>
<i>III</i>	<i>Farm First community to help small farmers share and learn the best methods for sustainable farming practice.</i>
<i>IV</i>	<i>A platform to manage medical resources in a sustainable manner.</i>

Table 1. Illustrates some of the solutions proposed in response to the SDG challenge.

Through this process of active learning, students were able to try out ideas without the fear of failure, push ideas to one side and go in new directions if the need arose, test, review, and revise ideas through feedback, constantly assessing for costs and benefits.

Some of the lessons learnt for IS education and the use of active learning for sustainable business solutions are; know the market – design for a section of the economy, one size does not fit all, check local policy and regulations to make sure the design fits the context, design a flexible business model to support resilience to challenges, and create solutions that are tangible, simple, realistic and sustainable. As IS educators, we can support students' experiential journeys to explore sustainability objectives in the classroom by providing opportunities for variation and experimentation.

The case study demonstrated the effectiveness of active learning techniques in promoting sustainability challenges and engaging students in developing innovative, sustainable solutions. These findings have important implications for IS education and sustainable business solutions, highlighting the need for tailored, context-specific approaches that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital social innovation.

Keywords: *IS Education, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Design Thinking, Active Learning, Digital Social Innovation.*

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